

MECHANISMS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF METHODOLOGICAL WORK BY DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE HEADS OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION

Kurbanov Ibratbek G'ayrat ugli

Independent researcher of Urgench State University

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Abstract: In this thesis, the theoretical foundations of improving the effectiveness of methodological work and improving the methodology of developing the professional competence of leaders by developing the professional competence of pedagogues in preschool educational organizations are explained.

Key words: preschool education, future leaders, science and education, creativity, professional competence, creative competence.

Introduction:

Formation and development process of vocational education, laws and trends, problems of preparing future teachers for professional pedagogical activities R.Kh.Djuraev, P.T.Magzumov, U.N. Nishonaliev, A.R. Khodjabaev, H.F. Rashidov, U.I. Inoyatov, B.L. Farberman et all. Theoretical perception of competent approach E.F. Zeer, I.A. Zimnyaya, V. Khutorskiy's prohibitions, while N.A. Kiselev, Ye.V. Lebedev, S.A. Novikova, N.V. Popov, V.M. Shepel The works of scientists such as are dedicated. The scientific researches of G.I. Khasanova, G, Q, Karimova are aimed at increasing the professional competence of the head pedagogues of the preschool education system.

Despite the importance of the conducted work, in our opinion, the problem of formation of professional competence of head pedagogues of preschool education organization has not been sufficiently researched. Research shows that competencies "are the expected and measurable achievements of an individual, which determine what the individual can do after the completion of the educational process; a generalized feature that determines the readiness of a specialist to use all his potential (knowledge, skills, experience and personal qualities) for successful work in a certain professional field". Based on the above definitions, it is possible to present the important content of the concept of "professional competence", which is considered in acmeology in its department of developmental psychology as the main cognitive component of the subsystems of human professional skills and the implementation of professional activities with high productivity. The structure and content of professional

powers are mainly determined by the specific characteristics of professional activity, its belonging to certain types.

Analysis of the essence of the concept of "professional competence", the integration of knowledge, experience and professionally important personal qualities that reflect the teacher's (teacher's) ability to effectively implement professional activities and achieve goals related to personality development in the preschool education system and this is possible if the subject of professional activity has achieved a certain level of professionalism.

Professionalism in psychology and acmeology is a high level of readiness to perform professional tasks, qualitative characteristics of the subject of work, high professional skills and qualifications, reflecting various effective professional skills and abilities, including creative solutions, modern algorithms and solutions. Professional tasks that allow you to perform activities with high and stable productivity. At the same time, a person's professional skills are also distinguished, which also reflects high-level professionally important or personal and business qualities of the subject of work, professional skills, creativity, sufficient level of aspiration, motivational sphere and value directions aimed at the progressive development of the person. is understood as an indicator.

As a result of the analysis of pedagogical experience and scientific research on a global scale, it has been proven that 70% of all the knowledge that a person acquires during his life is acquired before the age of five. In fact, during this period, the child begins to perceive the world, thinks, gets to know the environment, and prepares the ground for the knowledge he will receive throughout his life. The role of pre-school education organizations and specialists of pre-school education organizations is incomparable in educating the young generation, who are considered the future of our country, as well-rounded individuals.

Improvement of the method of developing creative competence of future specialists working in preschool educational organizations based on an integrative approach shows the useful and necessary aspects of future specialists in demonstrating their creative and creative abilities in any process. A pedagogue working in pre-school educational organizations to develop the creative abilities of the growing young generation to fully respond to the demands of the new age, to creatively approach any situation, to understand the world with new views, to form creative thinking and thinking in them, demands creative competence from specialists in their professional activities. The

development of creative competence of the future leaders and specialists of the preschool educational organization, whose role is incomparable in the development of a perfect person, is primarily the responsibility of the pedagogues of the higher education institution. According to data (according to youth psychology), children under the age of six have 40% talent potential. Children are very prone to creativity and creativity from the youngest age.

Therefore, this period is the right time for children to develop their creative abilities. For this, creative quality and creative competence must be formed in the specialists of the preschool education organization. The addition of the subject "Fundamentals of creative pedagogy" to the current educational process in the training of future leaders studying at a higher educational institution, the development of creative competence necessary for future professional activities of students, serves to organize the educational process effectively and qualitatively. We are not mistaken when we say that it will be the determining factor. According to the concept of preschool education, the priority tasks of preschool education are as follows: personal development of the child, caring for his emotional well-being, development of imagination and creativity, formation of children's ability to cooperate with other people. These tasks are determined by the relationship to preschool age as a unique and valuable period of personal development.

The value of the period of preschool development and its permanent importance for all subsequent human life imposes a special responsibility on preschool leaders. Solving the main tasks before preschool educational institutions, new goals and content of alternative programs of preschool education, rejecting the manipulative approach to the child, the educational and disciplinary model of interaction with him, expect new relationships between adults and children. In order to have a holistic view of the possible methods and methods of forming the professional competences of preschool leaders, we will consider the main concepts: competence, professional competence.

For many researchers, the competence of a specialist is primarily manifested in the effective performance of functional tasks. But competence is also understood in this way: the measure of awareness of the surrounding world and the adequacy of interaction with it; a set of knowledge, skills and competences that allow to successfully perform the activity; a certain level of formation of social and practical experience of the subject; the level of preparation for social and individual forms of activity that allow a person to work successfully in society within his abilities and position; a set of

professional characteristics, i.e. Ability to fulfill work requirements to a certain extent, etc. The head of a preschool educational organization should have the following social and professional competencies that allow children to develop cognitively:

1. Social competencies include the exchange of information between individuals, the expression of their interests and needs, the manifestation of tolerance towards other people and their opinions, the ability to work in a team and various support for other people with emotional stability includes the ability to give;

2. Cognitive competences are manifested in the independent processing and structure of information, in the search for new sources of information, in concentrating on studying or working, in the ability to use the acquired knowledge and skills.

3. Operational competences - setting goals and work order, the ability to resist ambiguity and uncertainty, the ability to make and implement decisions, summarize work results, determine the work schedule;

4. Special competencies include methods of problem solving, self-management, being active in professional activities, adapting to new situations, evaluating and correcting plans, identifying errors and planning adequate ways to eliminate them.

Conclusion:

Therefore, professional competences are the basis for introducing a competence approach to the pedagogical process, and the preschool educational organization helps the leader in the implementation of innovative activities and the practical use of modern educational technologies. Also, the leader should have the characteristic of mental activity: verbal-logical memory, the characteristic of activity goals: involuntary memory, according to the storage period of the material: short-term memory. The leader must be psychologically ready for professional activity, in particular, the leader needs stress resistance, the ability to control his behavior and emotions, and a strong nervous system: even if the work of the leader is not enhanced by physical strength, constant psycho- continues under conditions of emotional stress. It is necessary for the pedagogue leader to have high professional competence in the formation of preschool children in all aspects.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 30-sentabrdagi "Maktabgacha ta'limtizimi boshqaruvini tubdan takomillashtirish choratadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PF5198-sonli Farmoni. 2017-yil 30-sentabr. Qonun

hujjatlari ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi, 30.09.2017 y., 06/17/5198/0043-son;
09.10.2020 y., 07/20/4857/1357-son.

2. O'zbekiston respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2020-yil 22 dekabrda
"Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiyaning Davlat standartini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"
802-son Qarori / qonun hujjatlari ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi, 23.12.2020
y.,09/20/802/1658-son

3. "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya" to'g'risidagi Qonun. O'RQ 595. 16.12.2019
yil.

4. Sharifzoda, S. O. Strategies for forming competencies in students based on
an integrative approach. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary
Research and Management Studies/ISSN, 2750-8587.

5. "Talabalarda kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishda integrativ yondashuvdan
foydalanishning mazmuni va metodlari" S.O Sharifzoda - Ilm sarchashmalari.-
1.2023 йил. Б

6. Factors For Preparing Students For Pedagogical Activities Aimed At
Socialization On The Basis Of A Gender Approach, S.SHARIFZODA - ... Conference
on Management, Economics & Social ..., 2023

7. "Ўқувчиларда Таянч Компетенцияларни Шакллантиришда
Интегратив Ёндашувдан Фойдаланиш: Шарифзоди Сардорбек Ўразбой
табиб ўғли, Урганч давлат университети Педагогика факультети
педагогика ва психология кафедраси таянч докторанти" СУ Шарифзоди -
Образование и инновационные исследования ..., 2021

8. "Some important issues in the use of integrated learning materials" S.U
Sharifzoda - Актуальные Вопросы Современной Науки, 2021

9. "Ўқувчиларда таянч компетенцияларни шакллантириш асосида
ижтимоий компетентликни таркиб топтириш мазмуни" S.O Sharifzoda -
Academic research in educational sciences, 2021

10. Integrativ yondashuvdan foydalanib o'quvchilarda tayanch
kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishning didaktik asoslari, "Ўзбекистонда илмий-
амалий тадқиқотлар" 30-кўп тармоқли илмий масофавий онлайн
конференция материаллари тўплами 31 июль 2021 йил SO Sharifzoda -
Тошкент:«Tadqiqot, 2021

11. Интегратив ёндашув асосида ўқувчиларда таянч компетенцияларни
шакллантириш имкониятлари SO Sharifzoda - Замонавий фан ва таълим:
илмий услубий тўплам ..., 2021

12. "Талаба ёшлар маънавиятини шакллантиришда оиланинг аҳамияти"
SO Sharifzoda - ... перспективы развития науки и образования в ..., 2017

13. Pedagogical conditions for the organization of gender based training
Innovative research in modern education” S.O Sharifzoda - Hosted from Toronto,
Canada30

